

AGEMERA PROJECT STUDIES LOCAL PEOPLE'S PERCEPTIONS: IS THE MINERAL INDUSTRY SUPPORTING THE FUTURE OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES?

by

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Recognising and respecting local people's opinions on mineral exploration and mining are a necessity for the mineral industry. Failing to do so damages a company's reputation and the local acceptance of a project. This may seriously harm not just the individual project, but the legitimacy of the entire industry. Bad news spreads quickly in this globalised world, especially via social media (Ernst & Young 2020, 2022, Suopajarvi et al. 2022).

One important task in AGEMERA (2023) WP2 is to study local people's perceptions of mineral exploration and mining. For this purpose, the University of Lapland with its WP2 partners designed a questionnaire concerning the social impacts and acceptance of mineral exploration and mining, and the mineral industry's role in developing sustainable communities.

The survey was piloted in Northern Finland between 3 February and 3 March 2023. The data were collected through an online survey published on the website of the University of Lapland and promoted on several local Facebook forums. The survey targeted the residents of Kuusamo, Posio, and Rovaniemi municipalities, as these are potential target areas of AGEMERA field studies (Table 1).

We received 293 responses, mostly from residents of Kuusamo and Rovaniemi. The mean age of the sample was 52 years and most respondents were men. Most had higher education and were employed. They came from various employment sectors with no significant preponderance in any one sector. The vast majority of the respondents had lived in the aforementioned municipalities for over 10 years and most were planning to stay in their home municipalities in the long term.

Table 1. Municipality of residence.

Total (n)	Kuusamo	Posio	Rovaniemi	Outside the research area	Did not respond
293	116	13	107	46	11

For the analysis presented in this abstract, only respondents living permanently in Kuusamo, Posio, or Rovaniemi were included.

In the analyses, social license to operate (SLO) refers to the local acceptance of mines in the respondents' home region. People could respond to the statement "I approve of mining in my home region" using a five-point Likert scale in which 1 = completely disagree, 2 = somewhat disagree, 3 = neither agree nor disagree, 4 = somewhat agree, and 5 = completely agree. In this presentation, the response option "I don't know" has been omitted from the analysis. The responses were interpreted as follows: 1 = resistance, 2 = refusal, 3 = no clear opinion, 4 = acceptance, and 5 = support.

Those who decided to complete the questionnaire clearly had an opinion on mining, and fewer than 4% of the respondents had no clear opinion. Of the respondents, half were critical of mining in their home area and almost half (46%) were pro-mining. The views of male respondents were equally divided for and against, whereas females were slightly more critical, with 51% opposing and 43% supporting mining. In this case, therefore, gender did not explain the acceptance/non-acceptance of mining as opinions were divided among both women and men. When comparing acceptance with level of education, people with higher education seemed to be more pro-mining, as 56% of them accepted or supported mining.

As often repeated in the academic literature, local acceptance of mining is context specific. In this survey, 61% of respondents living in the Kuusamo-Posio area did not accept mining in their home area, whereas only 38% of respondents from Rovaniemi rejected mining. The reason for this difference may be that information about the survey reached different kinds of people in different regions. As well, Kuusamo already has organised resistance to mining, namely, the Pro Kuusamo association, which is celebrating its tenth anniversary in 2023 (Pro Kuusamo 2023). Also, a clear majority of local decision-makers at the municipal level have opposed mining (e.g., Iltalehti 2021).

Accordingly, 92% of respondents who did not accept mining disagreed with the statement "Large-scale mining projects are necessary for the vitality of my home region", whereas 70% of those who accepted mining agreed with the statement. More than half of those who accepted mining (category 4 in the five-point Likert scale) did not see large-scale mining as a necessity for the locality. Hence, those who approved of mining also had critical views of the industry.

As SLO refers to present-day acceptance, we included questions about respondents' perceptions of the future of the locality and what role mining might play in it. At the moment, there is no operating mine in the research area, but mineral exploration is intensive there (Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency 2023). A mining project developed by Suhanko Arctic Platinum Oy is ongoing on the southern border of Rovaniemi, where the company is expecting to start production in 2026 (Suhanko Arctic Platinum Oy 2023).

Respondents were asked: 1) When you think about the year 2050, what do you consider the biggest threats to your home region? 2) What is the best that can happen to your home region by 2050? The rationale behind these questions was to understand how mining is seen as part of the local future and local sustainability. As often repeated in the academic discussions, "sustainable development" is difficult to define, even being seen as an oxymoron, and the definition depends on each actor's own point of view (see, e.g., Lempinen 2019, McDonagh et al. 2020). To accommodate this, the questions were open-ended, and in fact, different respondents used different concepts of "sustainability" or "sustainable" in different contexts.

Those who opposed mining were mainly concerned about the environment. Pollution and the destruction of nature were seen as the biggest threats, and these

factors were usually associated with potential mining. However, environmental concern was not limited to these specific issues. Climate change was also viewed as a shared threat, as many of those who accepted mining were concerned about its impacts as well. Supporters of mines did not discuss environmental hazards, but instead the economic decline of the home region.

Sustainability, or more precisely its conceptual predecessor sustainable development, has been analytically divided into three pillars – environmental, economic, and social sustainability – ever since the Brundtland Commission introduced the concept to a broad audience (WCED 1987). According to our empirical data, these pillars are often inseparable from one another, and two aspects of sustainability were often intertwined in participants' responses. For example, "clean and vital nature" was seen as the most valuable asset for tourism, specifically, what is called "nature-based tourism". In the mining supporters' responses, economic development was often equated with industrial development and mining, as a necessity for population growth and demographic rejuvenation.

The vision of opportunity, hope, and positive development for the home area in 2050 was clear: a diverse economic structure, no matter one's opinion on mines. However, perceptions of how economic diversity should be built varied between the opponents and supporters of mining. People who did not want mines in their home region promoted a combination of nature-based tourism and the harvesting and refining of natural products, including the small-scale wood-processing industry. Those who supported mining development argued that, alongside tourism, there should also be other sectors for livelihoods, i.e., mining and industry in general. What worried the respondents most of all was dependency on only one sector for livelihoods, making living in the home area more vulnerable to global economic fluctuations.

To understand SLO in mineral exploration and mining, "local context is the key" as Jason Prno (2013) has argued. But what exactly are the factors that affect acceptance? The answer can be found, for example, by a comparative study. That is why the survey will be administered in 2023–2024 in the AGEMERA partners' research areas in different countries. How do local conditions and the operating practices of different companies, for example, affect the acceptability of the mineral industry, locally as well as in society more generally? Also, it is particularly important to know how the mineral industry can support and strengthen the future of local communities.

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